

Oxidation of Carbohydrates, Fats and Nitrogenous Substances by Hydrogen Peroxide and Ferric Salts.

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In a series of publications from this laboratory, the slow and induced oxidation of organic and inorganic substances has been investigated (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1922, **122**, 146 ; 1925, **144**, 289 ; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, **28**, 943 ; 1925, **29**, 376, 799 ; 1926, **30**, 939 ; 1928, **32**, 1263, 1663) and the mechanism of the oxidation in the animal body has been imitated. It is well known that the edible substances like carbohydrates, fats and proteins are very readily oxidised in the body, whereas they are oxidised with difficulty in the laboratory. But in the papers referred to, it has been shown that the edible substances can be oxidised in the laboratory also at the ordinary temperature by passing air, if inductors like ferrous hydroxide, cerous hydroxide, sodium sulphite, etc., are present. It is interesting to note that these edible substances can be oxidised by passing air through them if they are exposed to sunlight even without any catalyst. In each of these cases, complete oxidation to carbon dioxide takes place. Even complex substance like butter, lecithin, milk, egg-white, egg-yellow, cholesterol, etc., are oxidised almost quantitatively into carbon dioxide and water.

We know that a deviation from this rule is found in animal bodies during certain diseases and also during fasting. In diabetic patients, glucose is practically not oxidised and acetone bodies are found in the organism. In normal health, the heat and energy of the body is derived from the simultaneous and slow combustion of carbohydrates, fats and nitrogenous substances. But in diabetes, the carbohydrates are not oxidised. Hence, in order to supply the necessary heat and energy to the body, the oxidation of fats and nitrogenous substances has to become more rapid than in normal health. It appears, therefore, that when the oxidation of fats and nitrogenous substances is more rapid than in normal health, acetone bodies are likely to be formed. The acetone bodies are also formed during long fasting. In starvation, the necessary amount of heat and energy is obtained from the body itself and the glycogen store in the body is first oxidised. When the glycogen is exhausted, in order to bring in the same amount of energy, a more rapid oxidation of the body tissues and body fats takes place with the result that acetone bodies

are formed. Dakin (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1908, **4**, 77) had shown that ammonium butyrate, on being oxidised with hydrogen peroxide, produced acetone, acetoacetic acid, acetaldehyde, etc. As hydrogen peroxide is believed to be a more rapid oxidising agent than air, it was thought desirable to investigate the oxidation of edible substances with hydrogen peroxide and ferric salt as an accelerator, in order to find out the nature of the change occurring if the oxidation in animal body becomes more rapid than in normal health. In the present paper, the oxidation of edible substances either occurring singly or in mixtures, by hydrogen peroxide and ferric salt, has been investigated and our results are likely to throw considerable light on the metabolism in diabetes and in starvation.

In several publications from these laboratories we have proved that the slow oxidation of substances can be retarded by another reducing agent which usually undergoes slow oxidation along with the primary change (*Proc. Akad. Wet., Amsterdam*, 1921, **29**, 1023; *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1925, **144**, 289; cf. Moureaux and Dufraisse, *Compt. rend.*, 1924, **179**, 237). Thus we have shown that the oxidation of sodium sulphite by air is markedly retarded by sodium arsenite which undergoes oxidation by air in presence of sodium sulphite. Similarly we have proved that the slow oxidation of carbohydrates by air is retarded by fats and nitrogenous substances and the oxidation of fats and nitrogenous substances is retarded by the presence of glucose. In the present paper, we have also investigated the retardation of the oxidation of one edible substance by hydrogen peroxide in presence of another.

EXPERIMENTAL.

10 C.c. of 1% solution of carbohydrates, fats and nitrogenous substances were mixed with 10 c.c. of hydrogen peroxide (Merck's, 12% by vol.) and 1 c.c. of ferric sulphate solution containing 0.005 gm. of iron. The mixture was kept at 37° (body temperature) in a thermostat for 5 hours. The products were carefully distilled by heating the mixture for forty-five minutes over the direct flame of a Bunsen burner. The distillate and the residue were treated with the following reagents:—(i) Fehling's solution; (ii) Schiff's reagent, (iii) mercuric chloride, (iv) ammoniacal silver nitrate, (v) bromine water, (vi) calcium chloride and (vii) iodine with caustic soda. The smell of the products was also noted. The results are tabulated in the Table I.

In the cases of potassium palmitate, stearate and oleate, the smell of acrolein could be distinctly perceived in the distillate, and in the last case, the smell was very strong. In the case of lactic acid and alanine, a distinct smell of acetaldehyde was found. But in the majority of cases the products could not be definitely identified because they contain numerous ingredients. The volatile aldehydic and ketonic products were estimated in the following way :—

The above mixture of the edible substances, hydrogen peroxide and ferric salt, after keeping at 37° for 5 hours, was taken out and the volume was made up to 50 c.c. in every case. They were then distilled slowly for 45 minutes in the usual way and the distillate absorbed in water. 10 C.c. of *N*/10-caustic soda and 10 c.c. of *N*/10-iodine solution were then added to the distillate and kept aside for ten minutes. A portion of the iodine was taken up by the aldehydic products and iodoform was produced in appreciable quantities in the cases of fats, and some nitrogenous substances. The solution was acidified with 10 c.c. of *N*/10-sulphuric acid and the liberated iodine was titrated against *N*/10-sodium thiosulphate, thus giving the amount of iodine taken up by the volatile products. The results are given in Tables II—V.

TABLE II.

Carbohydrate taken=0.1 gm. Hydrogen peroxide=10 c.c.
Amount of iron in ferric sulphate=0.005 gm. Time of oxidation=5 hrs. Temperature=15°. Total volume =50 c.c.

Carbohydrate : Glucose. Fructose. Lactose. Arabinose. Galactose. Maltose.
Amount of
N/10-iodine 2.6 c.c. 3.2 c.c. 3.8 c.c. 3.5 c.c. 4.2 c.c. 6.0 c.c.
absorbed :

Carbohydrate : Sucrose. Starch. Dextrin. Inulin. Glycogen.
Amount of
N/10-iodine 1.7 c.c. 2.6 c.c. 3.3 c.c. 3.3 c.c. 4.2 c.c.
absorbed :

TABLE III.

Nitrogenous substance taken=0.1 gm. (0.5 gm in the case of urea). Hydrogen peroxide=10 c.c. Amount of iron in ferric sulphate=0.005 gm. Time of oxidation=5 hrs. Temperature=37°. Total volume=50 c.c.

Nitrogenous substance : Alanine. Glycine. Egg-white. Egg-yellow. Urea.
Amount of *N*/10-iodine
absorbed in c.c. : 3.70 3.40 3.80 3.30 nil

TABLE IV.

Amount of fats taken = 0.1 gm. (0.462 gm. in the case of butter).
 Hydrogen peroxide = 10 c.c. (20 c.c. in the case of butter).
 Amount of iron in ferric sulphate = 0.005 gm.
 Time of oxidation = 5 hrs. (24 hrs. in the case of butter).
 Temperature = 37°. Total volume = 50 c.c.

Fats	:	K-oleate	K-stearate.	K-palmitate.	Butter.
Amount of N/10-iodine absorbed in c.c. :		4.3	2.4	4.6	5.6

TABLE V.

Cholesterol + Hydrogen Peroxide + Fe₂(SO₄)₃.

Volume = 50 c.c.

Amount of cholesterol.	Amount of H ₂ O ₂ .	Amount of iron	Temp.	Time.	Amount of N/10-iodine absorbed.
0.5 g.	20 c.c.	0.009 g.	37°.	24 hrs.	2.6 c.c.

The mutual retardation in the oxidation of the food materials with hydrogen peroxide and ferric salt was measured in the following way: 10 c.c. each of carbohydrates and nitrogenous substances were mixed and 20 c.c. of hydrogen peroxide were added. The temperature was kept at 37° but the time of the reaction was extended to 25 hours. After the reaction, the volume was made up to 100 c.c. and the distillation carried on for about an hour and a quarter. The distillate was absorbed in water and 20 c.c. of N/10-NaOH and 20 c.c. of N/10-iodine were added and the residual iodine estimated in the usual way. Similar treatment was made in the mixtures of carbohydrates and fats, and fats and nitrogenous substances. In the mixture of all the three varieties, the amount of hydrogen peroxide was increased to 20 c.c., and the time was extended to 48 hours. The results are tabulated in Tables VI–XI.

TABLE VI.

Carbohydrates + Nitrogenous Substances + H₂O₂ + Fe₂(SO₄)₃.

Hydrogen peroxide = 20 c.c. Carbohydrate = 0.1 gm. Nitrogenous matter = 0.1 gm.

Iron=0.005 gm. Temperature=37°. Time=24 hours. Total volume=100 c.c. Egg-white or yellow = 0.5 gm.

Carbohydrates.	Alanine (3.7).	Glycine (3.4).	Urea (x).	Egg-white (3.8).	Egg-yellow. (3.3).
Glucose (2.6)	5.3 c.c.	3.6 c.c.	2.5 c.c.	3.1 c.c.	1.9 c.c.
Fructose (3.2)	3.7	2.1	...	2.3	3.2
Lactose (3.8)	4.0	3.6	...	1.6	6.7
Arabinose (3.5)	1.9	3.7	...	4.4	4.8
Galactose (4.2)	4.7	4.4	...	4.8	5.1
Maltose (6.0)	5.2	4.2	...	1.9	6.2
Sucrose (1.7)	3.2	2.9	...	2.1	6.2
Starch (2.6)	1.8	4.8	...	3.3	3.7
Inulin (3.3)	2.7	3.1	...	2.7	3.5
Dextrin (3.3)	4.8	2.4	...	2.5	5.3
Glycogen (4.2)	3.9	4.3	...	2.6	5.9

N. B.—The figures in the brackets in the above and all subsequent tables show the amount of *N*/10-iodine absorbed by the single substance after oxidation. The other figures indicate the amount of *N*/10-iodine absorbed by the mixtures after oxidation.

TABLE VII.

Carbohydrates + Fats + Hydrogen Peroxide + Fe₂(SO₄)₃.

Hydrogen peroxide=20 c.c. Carbohydrate=0.1 gm. Fat=0.1 gm. (butter=0.462 gm.) Iron=0.005 gm. Temperature=37°. Time=25 hours (72 hrs. in the case of the mixture with butter). Total volume = 100 c.c.

	K-oleate (4.9)	K-stearate (2.4)	K-palmitate (4.6)	Butter (5.6)
Glucose (2.6)	5.2 c.c.	2.6 c.c.	4.7 c.c.	6.3 c.c.
Fructose (3.2)	1.1	1.9	4.6	3.9
Lactose (3.8)	4.6	4.6	3.8	5.9
Arabinose (3.5)	5.5	3.3	2.1	6.7
Galactose (4.2)	5.7	4.3	5.3	6.6
Maltose (6.0)	5.7	2.0	4.5	6.0
Sucrose (1.7)	2.2	1.3	1.7	5.1
Starch (2.6)	2.5	1.1	2.2	4.9
Inulin (3.3)	6.3	5.6	6.0	6.0
Dextrin (3.3)	3.2	3.6	3.6	3.2
Glycogen (4.2)	6.7	6.4	6.0	3.7

TABLE VIII.

Fats + Nitrogenous Substances + Hydrogen Peroxide + Fe₂(SO₄)₃.

Hydrogen peroxide = 20 c.c. Fats = 0.1 gm. (butter = 0.462 gm).
 Nitrogenous substances = 0.1 gm. (egg-white or -yellow = 0.5 gm).
 Iron = 0.005 gm. Temperature = 37°. Time = 25 hours (72 hrs. in
 the case of the mixture with butter). Total volume = 100 c.c.

	Alanine. (3.7)	Glycine. (3.4)	Urea (x)	White-egg. (3.8)	Egg-yellow. (3.3).
Potassium oleate (4.9)	4.6 c.c.	2.3 c.c.	2.9 c.c.	3.3 c.c.	6.6 c.c.
Potassium stearate (2.4)	2.1	3.5	2.2	3.8	6.9
Potassium palmitate (4.6)	4.1	3.1	1.2	6.4	6.7
Butter (5.6)	4.4	6.7	...	4.4	6.5

TABLE IX.

Cholesterol + Fats + Hydrogen Peroxide + Fe₂(SO₄)₃.

Hydrogen peroxide = 30 c.c. Fats = 0.1 gm. Cholesterol = 0.5 gm.
 Iron = 0.005 gm. Temperature = 37°. Time = 60 hours. Total
 volume = 100 c.c.

	Potassium stearate. (2.4)	Potassium pal (4.7)	Potassium oleate. (4.9)
Cholesterol (2.6)	4.0 c.c.	5.6 c.c.	4.7 c.c.

TABLE X.

*Carbohydrates + Fats + Nitrogenous Substances + Hydrogen
 Peroxide + Fe₂(SO₄)₃.*

Carbohydrates, oleate, stearate and palmitate = 0.1 gm. each.
 Butter = 0.462 gm. Egg-white or -yellow = 0.5 gm. each.
 Hydrogen peroxide = 30 c.c. Iron = 0.005 gm. Temperature = 37°. Time = 53 hours. Total volume = 100 c.c.

Mixtures.	Amount of N/10-iodine absorbed.		
Glycogen (4.2)	+ Alanine (3.7)	+ Oleate (4.8)	6.0 c.c.
"	"	+ Stearate (2.5)	4.8
"	"	+ Palmitate (4.4)	6.1
Butter (5.6)	+ Egg-white (3.8)	+ Glucose (2.6)	5.3
"	"	+ Sucrose (1.7)	3.1
"	"	+ Starch (2.6)	5.2
"	"	+ Inulin (3.3)	3.6
"	"	+ Dextrin (3.3)	5.6
"	"	+ Glycogen (4.2)	3.8

TABLE X—*contd.*

Mixtures	Amount of N/10-iodine absorbed.
Butter (5·6) + Egg-yellow (3·3) + Glucose (2·6)	8·3 c.c.
.. .. + Sucrose (1·7)	7·3
.. .. + Starch (2·6)	6·6
.. .. + Inulin (3·3)	9·6
.. .. + Dextrin (3·3)	8·6
.. .. + Glycogen (4·2)	6·8

TABLE XI.

Carbohydrates + Fats + Hydrogen Peroxide + Fe₂(SO₄)₃.

Hydrogen peroxide = 75 c c. Carbohydrate = 0·5 gm. Oleate = 0·2 gm. Butter = 0·925 gm. Iron = 0·005 gm. Temperature = 37°. Time = 5⁰ hours. Total volume = 150 c.c.

Mixtures.	Amount of N/10-iodine absorbed.
Glucose (12) + Oleate (10·1)	8·2 c.c.
Starch (12·2) ..	5·3
Sucrose (9) ..	5·1
Dextrin (15) ..	7·4
Glycogen (19·8) ..	6·9
Inulin (15·2) ..	8·4
Glucose (12) + Butter (11·5)	9·9
Starch (12·2) ..	5·6
Sucrose (9) ..	5·5
Dextrin (15) ..	7·8
Glycogen (19·8) ..	8·3
Inulin (15·2) ..	9·8

A glance at the above table shows that in each case a certain amount of iodine has been taken up by the volatile product showing that substances of aldehydic or ketonic nature have been produced during the reaction. The amount of the substances of aldehydic or ketonic nature formed is greatest in the case of fats, specially butter and least in the case of carbohydrates, specially sucrose. It is interesting to note that not only do the fats and nitrogenous substances produce compounds of aldehydic or ketonic nature but even the carbohydrates produce substances of this type. The explanation is not far to seek. The carbohydrates on oxidation gives rise to glyceric aldehyde, pyruvic aldehyde, pyruvic acid and lactic acid. Lactic acid

very easily oxidises to acetaldehyde (*cf.* Ray, *J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1924, 6, 509, 528).

The higher fatty acids gradually oxidise into the lower fatty acids due to β -oxidation (*Beitr. Chem. Physiol. Path.*, 1908, 22, 411) and ultimately to butyric acid from which the production of acetone bodies can be explained. The amino-acids on oxidation give the hydroxy-acids, the lower acids and ultimately aldehydic and ketonic products. It has been known from a long time that alanine can produce acetaldehyde on oxidation, and hence if the proteins hydrolyse to the stage of amino-acids, as it usually does in the body, the production of alanine or similar products can explain the formation of acetone bodies from the proteins.

It is interesting to note from the foregoing data that, in mixtures, the amount of iodine absorbed by the volatile products after oxidation with hydrogen peroxide is remarkably reduced showing that the amount of the substances of aldehydic nature is decreased. The retardation is greatest in the case of starch and sucrose. Table XI shows that if the amount of carbohydrates be increased the amount of aldehydic product is still more decreased. Hence the presence of carbohydrates decreases the amount of acetone bodies formed by the oxidation of fats by hydrogen peroxide and ferric salts.

It appears therefore that some methods of treatment in diabetes are faulty. A school of medical men prefer the administration of fats to diabetic patients arguing that as glucose cannot be oxidised in the body, the required energy must be supplied by fat. But our results show that in the absence of glucose, fats cannot be oxidised in the normal manner. On the contrary, they produce poisonous bodies like acetone, diacetic acid, etc. So the more the patient gets fats, the more is the quantity of acetone bodies formed and thus the end of the patient is likely to be hastened. Similar arguments can be brought against those who prefer protein ingestion. In order that the oxidation in the animal body should proceed in the normal manner, glucose must be oxidised. So the treatment of diabetic patients should depend upon the fundamental principle that the glucose must be more largely oxidised.

It is well known that by the injection of insulin, acetone bodies disappear from the body. This is due to the fact that by the presence of insulin, the glucose, which was passing unoxidised from the diabetic system, is oxidised and the oxidation of the glucose leads to the more complete though more slow oxidation of fats.

Summary.

(1) Sugars, starch, glycogen, dextrin, inulin, alanine, egg-white, egg-yellow, butter, oleate, stearate, palmitate, etc., were oxidised with hydrogen peroxide and ferric salt and the volatile aldehydic or ketonic products were estimated by the amount of iodine taken up by them in the formation of iodoform. It has been proved that not only the fats but the carbohydrates and nitrogenous substances have the property of producing acetone bodies.

(2) The oxidation of the mixtures of fats and proteins fats and carbohydrates, carbohydrates and proteins and the mixture of all the three varieties by hydrogen peroxide and ferric salt has been investigated and it has been shown that in mixtures, the amount of acetone bodies formed is markedly decreased. Thus the oxidation of fat is retarded by proteins and carbohydrates, the oxidation of protein is retarded by carbohydrates and fats and the oxidation of carbohydrates is retarded by fats and proteins.

(3) It has also been shown that in the oxidation of the mixtures of carbohydrates and fats with hydrogen peroxide and ferric salt, the amount of acetone bodies is decreased with the increase of the amount of carbohydrates.

(4) These experimental results are likely to throw considerable light on the metabolism in the animal body in normal health, in diabetes and in starvation.

(5) It seems that the disappearance of acetone bodies from the diabetic organism due to the injection of insulin is caused by the increased oxidation of the negative catalyst glucose.